

A SIMPLE PLASTICITY MODEL FOR PREDICTING TRANSVERSE COMPOSITE RESPONSE AND FAILURE

K.W. Gan*, M.R. Wisnom, S.R. Hallett, G. Allegri

Advanced Composites Centre for Innovation and Science, University of Bristol, University Walk, Bristol, BS8 1TR, United Kingdom.

* Corresponding author (khong.wui.gan@bristol.ac.uk)

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Abstract

This paper reports on the development of a simple three-parameter nonlinear constitutive model for composite materials. The model has been calibrated using two independent sets of experimental data in the literature. With knowledge of the critical tensile strain at failure of the matrix constituent, it is used to predict failure loads for load cases involving through-thickness compression and interlaminar shear, in which shear strengths increase with through-thickness compressive stresses. Good correlation with the experiments has been achieved.

Introduction

Composite materials exhibit highly non-linear constitutive responses in the matrix-dominated directions. The non-linearity in response can be considered generally as plastic behaviour, although physically this might not be strictly correct. The non-linearity can as well be attributed to the effects of various damage mechanisms in the matrix. In aerospace applications, the matrices are very often polymeric materials such as epoxy resins. Very distinctive differences exist between metals and polymers. Polymers in general display a strong pressure dependent material behaviour. In particular, the different yield behaviour between tension and compression of the polymeric matrix together with the anisotropic nature of composite materials precludes the use of a von-Mises type of yield criterion.

The purpose of this paper is to explore the potential use of a non-linear constitutive model to predict failure initiation in composites subjected to complex loading. The knowledge of strains gleaned from the constitutive model can be exploited so that the matrix dominated failure initiation can be estimated

with a simple maximum strain criterion. This is demonstrated with some load cases involving interlaminar shear and through-thickness compression supported by experimental measurements.

Development of the constitutive model

A non-linear elastoplastic constitutive law requires the definition of a yield function, which essentially defines the elastic limit of a material under combined states of stress. Ideally, a yield function for a unidirectional composite material should be formulated in the framework of transversely isotropic invariants, and be sufficiently simple to contain no more parameters than are necessary. The invariants, expressed in the conventional principal material axis notation of a unidirectional composite, are:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \sigma_1 \\ I_2 &= \sigma_2 + \sigma_3 \\ I_3 &= \tau_{13}^2 + \tau_{12}^2 \\ I_4 &= (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + 4\tau_{23}^2 \\ I_5 &= (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)(\tau_{13}^2 - \tau_{12}^2) - 4\tau_{23}\tau_{13}\tau_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

For most continuous fibre-reinforced composite materials, the response in the fibre direction from experimental observations is essentially linear to failure with no plastic deformation. Secondly, a yield criterion should not be dependent on the sign of shear stresses. Based on the above reasoning, the formulation of an appropriate yield function should exclude the first and the fifth invariants. A simple three-parameter plasticity yield function, f , similar to the Drucker-Prager model is proposed for this work.

$$f(\sigma_{ij}) = \sqrt{H(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + L\tau_{23}^2 + \tau_{13}^2 + \tau_{12}^2} + J(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \quad (2)$$

where H , L and J are material constants to be determined from the experiment data. Without loss of generality, the coefficient of the third invariant (the longitudinal shear terms) is arbitrarily set to 1, as this will facilitate the calibration process later. A strict adherence to the invariant formulation framework dictates $L = 4H$. However, due to the common lack of experimental data on the transverse shear response of composite materials and also to maintain the generality of the yield function, L is assumed to be an independent fitting parameter. All these material parameters are assumed to be constants and are independent of the stress state, i.e. the initial material orthotropy will not be affected by the subsequent plastic deformation.

Since this is a feasibility study and to keep the number of parameters to a minimum, an associative plastic flow rule is adopted, i.e. the plastic strain increment, $d\varepsilon_{ij}^p$, can be determined from the yield function itself via:

$$d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \frac{\partial f(\sigma_{ij})}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} d\lambda \quad (3)$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ and λ is the plastic multiplier to be defined later. In order to calibrate the yield function with the experimental uniaxial stress-strain curve, a scalar effective stress is defined:

$$\bar{\sigma} = f(\sigma_{ij}) \quad (4)$$

i.e. the effective stress is the same as the yield function in Equation (2). From the equivalence of the increment of plastic work per unit volume, we have:

$$dW_p = \sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \bar{\sigma} d\bar{\varepsilon}_p \quad (5)$$

where $d\bar{\varepsilon}_p$ is the increment of the effective plastic strain. Substituting Equation (3) into Equation (5) and using the definition from Equation (4):

$$\bar{\sigma} d\bar{\varepsilon}_p = \sigma_{ij} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} d\lambda = f d\lambda = \bar{\sigma} d\lambda \quad (6)$$

Therefore the plastic multiplier is equal to the effective plastic strain:

$$d\lambda = d\bar{\varepsilon}_p \quad (7)$$

By approximating the relation between effective stress and effective plastic strain of a simple uniaxial test using a Ramberg-Osgood equation:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_p = \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{K} \right)^n \quad (8)$$

where K and n are the curve fitting parameters, the magnitude of the plastic multiplier can be known from Equation (7) as a function of the effective stress. Experimental results for matrix-dominated responses in a fibre-reinforced composite very often do not indicate a well-defined yield point. To avoid an arbitrary definition of a yield point, the current constitutive model allows initial yielding at the moment the stresses are applied. Due to the power law nature of the Ramberg-Osgood equation, the amount of plastic strain will be negligibly small at low applied stresses. Also in this study, an isotropic hardening is assumed, i.e. any Bauschinger effect is neglected completely and the yield surface expands uniformly in all directions in the stress space. Residual thermal stresses are neglected.

Having the coefficient of the third invariant set to 1 in the yield function (Equation (2)) allows us to establish the effective stress and effective plastic strain relation solely from a simple longitudinal shear stress and plastic shear strain (τ_{12} - γ_{12}^p) response, without the need to know the values of H , L and J beforehand. In a pure longitudinal shear test, the effective stress is given by Equation (4) as:

$$\bar{\sigma} = \tau_{12} \quad (9)$$

while the effective plastic strain, from the equivalence of plastic work in Equation (5) and using Equation (7), becomes:

$$d\bar{\varepsilon}_p = d\gamma_{12} = d\lambda \quad (10)$$

Therefore the pure longitudinal shear stress-strain curve will act as the plasticity master curve which provides the essential information on the magnitude of the plastic multiplier as a function of the effective stress.

Calibration of the constitutive model

The aerospace graded carbon/epoxy IM7/8552 composite system is used here to assess the feasibility of this non-linear constitutive approach. For the master plasticity curve, the longitudinal shear stress-strain test data was taken from [1] (Figure 1). The corresponding shear stress-strain curve can be represented by Equation (8) with the fitting parameters $K = 167.27$ and $n = 0.184$.

Now the parameters H , L and J remain to be determined. Parameter L requires test data on the transverse shear stress-strain (τ_{23} - γ_{23}^p) response, which is difficult to measure and they are not readily available in the literature. The requirement that $L = 4H$ following the invariant formulation might make the transverse shear response overly compliant. Therefore, as a first approximation, the parameter L is set equal to 1, i.e. the plastic response of the transverse shear is assumed to be the same as that of the longitudinal shear. In fact, the expected value of L should not be much larger than 1.

On the other hand, the two unknown parameters H and J require two independent sets of test data which involve transverse normal stress-strain responses, such as the transverse tensile and compression tests, or the biaxial tests. They can be calibrated from the experimental work by Koerber et al. [2] who performed off-axis compression tests on carbon/epoxy IM7/8552 at six different off-axis angles: 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 75° and 90°. In the tests, the stress components along the principal material axes can be related to the off-axis applied axial stress, σ_x , as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{11} &= \sigma_x \cos^2 \theta \\ \sigma_{22} &= \sigma_x \sin^2 \theta \\ \tau_{12} &= -\sigma_x \sin \theta \cos \theta \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where θ is the off-axis angle. Similarly, the strain components along the principal material axes are related to the off-axis applied axial strain, ε_x , as:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{11} &= \varepsilon_x \cos^2 \theta \\ \varepsilon_{22} &= \varepsilon_x \sin^2 \theta \\ \gamma_{12} &= -2\varepsilon_x \sin \theta \cos \theta \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

For an infinitesimal stress increment, a separation of the increment strain tensor, $d\varepsilon_{ij}$ in the principal material axes into elastic strains, $d\varepsilon_{ij}^e$, and plastic strains, $d\varepsilon_{ij}^p$, is assumed:

$$d\varepsilon_{ij} = d\varepsilon_{ij}^e + d\varepsilon_{ij}^p \quad (13)$$

The elastic stress-strain relationship is given by the Hooke's Law for an orthotropic material. Equations (11) to (13) are substituted into Equations (2) to (10) to search for the optimal set of H and J values that best describe all the six off-axis compression experimental curves. As there are only two parameters to be determined, this can be easily done through a brute force optimisation process by searching through a range of possible H and J values that give the least squared error. This is done in MATLAB. It is found that $H = 0.34$ and $J = 0.26$ for the IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy composite.

The prediction of the plasticity model using the optimised parameters is compared against the six sets of off-axis experimental data in Figure 2 to Figure 7. Considering the simplicity of the model with only two main parameters, reasonably accurate constitutive responses for the composite material are obtained. The predicted stress-strain curves for small off-axis angles (fibre dominated) are slightly under-predicted, while they are over-predicted for large off-axis angles (matrix dominated). For moderate off-axis angles however, the agreement with the experimental curves is excellent. This model is now ready for use to predict material behavior in other more complex load cases, capturing phenomena or

stress states within composite structures that are unobtainable if a linear elastic analysis is used.

Case study

A case study is presented in this section to demonstrate the potential application for this simple plasticity model to predict the failure load of composite specimens subjected to through-thickness compression and interlaminar shear stress.

A symmetric version of the double-notch shear test has been proposed by the authors for direct measurement of the interlaminar shear strength under moderate through-thickness compression using a biaxial test rig (Figure 8) [3]. In the test, through-thickness compressive stresses were imposed through a pair of flat indenters with some user-specified loads. The interlaminar shear failure was designed to take place within the three plies of 0° at the gauge section of the specimen between the notches under longitudinal tensile loading. Thickness-wise away from the 0° plies, alternating 90° and 0° plies were present to prevent the specimens from splitting longitudinally so that the interlaminar shear strength of the specimens could be tested up to high through-thickness compressive loads. The test results show that the through-thickness compressive stress can significantly increase the interlaminar shear strength. The experimental results are shown in Figure 11.

In the following, a failure criterion for matrix dominated failure is proposed. Failure due to delamination is dominantly governed by the matrix strength properties. According to the Northwestern theory (the NU theory) developed in [4], a shear dominated failure criterion is governed by the limiting microscopic tensile strain set by pure shear in the ply interface region. Under pure shear loading in the 1-3 plane, the critical principal tensile strain at failure is one half of the shear strain at failure at 45° to the loading direction, as illustrated in Figure 9. For a biaxial σ_{33} - τ_{13} state of stress, failure is postulated to occur when the maximum principal tensile strain exceeds the critical principal tensile strain at failure given by the pure shear loading. In other words, it is essentially a maximum principal tensile strain criterion that predicts failure at the ply interface subjected to a σ_{33} - τ_{13} state of stress. Using

linear elastic stress-strain relationship, the failure criterion can be expressed in terms of the applied stresses and composite elastic properties as:

$$\left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + 2\frac{\sigma_{33}}{S_{13}}\frac{G_{13}}{E_3} = 1 \quad (14)$$

where S_{13} is the interlaminar shear strength, G_{13} is the shear modulus in the 1-3 plane and E_3 is the through-thickness elastic modulus of the composite. The NU theory (Equation (14)) prediction has shown good agreement with experimental results for interlaminar shear dominated failure in textile composites [4] involving interlaminar shear and through-thickness compression. The failure of the symmetric double-notch shear specimens [3] is also well-predicted using the NU theory.

In numerical modelling, a strain-based failure criterion such as the maximum strain criterion generally loses its appeal due to the difficulty in calculating the strains in a composite as they are usually highly non-linear with respect to the applied stresses. However, strains are fundamental quantities that can be measured directly in the experiments, unlike derived quantities such as stresses which need the precise knowledge of the material stiffness or require that the geometry of the specimen to be sufficiently simple. In addition to that, the maximum strain criterion also has the straightforward physical interpretation that a material fractures when two material points are separated by a critical displacement (or strain), regardless of the complexity of the load conditions.

The critical principal tensile strain at which the ply interface fails by interlaminar shear of IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy composite can be obtained from a simple shear test. Makeev and Seon [5] have measured the interlaminar shear stress-strain response for unidirectional IM7/8552 using short beam shear (SBS) specimens. The measured stresses were derived using a linear elastic beam theory so only first order accuracy was obtained. However, the strain values were obtained using digital image correlation (DIC) full-field technique. Provided that the technique was well calibrated, the strain measurement thus obtained was of higher accuracy.

In their SBS tests, the shear strain to failure was measured at about 3.9%, implying that the critical maximum principal tensile strain is 1.95% (half of the critical shear strain). Also the tensile strain to failure for the 8552 matrix constituent according to the datasheet provided by Hexcel [6] is 1.7%. Comparing the two values, it can therefore be estimated that the critical tensile strain to failure for a matrix dominated failure of IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy should be around 1.8%.

With the development of the current plasticity model, the total strains of composite materials can be obtained more accurately than those calculated using a linear elastic analysis. It is the purpose of this paper to demonstrate that a maximum principal tensile strain criterion (the NU theory) taking into account the non-linear stress-strain relation is still applicable in a non-linear analysis. The added advantage is that the non-linear model can give a more realistic global and local compliance response of the composite structure, which may alter the complex stress distribution within a complicated geometry. Using the authors' experimental results of the symmetric double-notch shear specimens made of IM7/8552 as an example, a 1.8% critical principal tensile strain failure criterion is used to predict failure loads.

In the initial study, the plasticity model is implemented in MATLAB as a single element with the material properties of IM7/8552 [3]. For simplicity, a two-dimensional plane strain boundary condition is assumed. Using the 1.8% critical principal tensile strain failure criterion, the results of both the linear elasticity and the plasticity models are compared against the experimental ones in Figure 11. Although both models display the trend of increasing interlaminar shear failure stress with transverse compression, the plasticity approach which incorporates a nonlinear constitutive response gives more realistic results. The linear elastic solution way overestimates the failure load. On the other hand, the slight overestimation of the failure load in the plasticity model can be attributed to the plane strain boundary condition, which tends to induce a higher hydrostatic pressure in the model, predicting the material to be less likely to yield and failure is thus delayed to a higher load.

For improvement of the numerical results, the proposed plasticity model is implemented in explicit solver LS-DYNA as a user-material subroutine to simulate the actual three-dimensional stress state. Only a quarter of the symmetric double-notch shear specimen (taking advantage of the symmetry boundary conditions) is modelled, as shown in Figure 10. Note that the current plasticity model does not incorporate a progressive damage or failed element deletion capability (this could be implemented in the future). This means that the global applied load of the model can continue to increase after the maximum strain criterion is reached, albeit at a decreasing rate due to the plasticity. To get over this, a user-defined definition of failure for the models needs to be prescribed. In this case, it is reasonable to define the failure load as the tensile load when at least 50% of the gauge section has reached 1.8% maximum principal tensile strain. This is illustrated in Figure 11, with the region in red showing "failed" elements within the gauge section. The shear strength is then simply calculated in an average sense as the tensile load divided by the gauge area. The improvement of the results can be seen in Figure 11.

It appears that the NU theory (Equation 14) can be used with success for both the linear elastic [3, 4] and the non-linear plasticity analyses to estimate the failure load in a biaxial shear-dominated failure. This can be explained qualitatively by examining Equation (14). Both the responses in the through-thickness normal direction and interlaminar shear are highly non-linear. The approximately equal degree of non-linearity of the two cancels each other out, therefore making the NU theory applicable for both solutions. However the general compliance response of a composite structure will be more accurate when the non-linearity in stress-strain relation is considered in the model.

Summary

A simple plasticity model for composite materials has been proposed. It takes into account the pressure effect and is able to capture the large strain and the nonlinear behaviour of the matrix caused by yield and flow. Neglecting these effects, a linear analysis tends to overestimate the stress-strain response and give inaccurate stress distributions in the material,

rendering precise failure predictions problematic, especially when involving complex multi-axial loading. This is demonstrated with an example of a biaxial load case involving interlaminar shear and through-thickness compressive normal stress, using a maximum principal tensile strain criterion. The plasticity model has been implemented as an explicit finite element subroutine in LS-DYNA and has proven to be a promising approach for studying matrix-dominated failure, at the same time giving a more realistic compliance response of a composite structure compared to a linear elastic model. This is especially the case when considering complex loading and stress states for which finite element analysis is the most suitable technique.

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Figures

Fig. 1. Non-linear shear stress vs. strain response for various UD composites [1].

Fig. 2. Stress-strain prediction of the plasticity model versus 15° off-axis compression test result [2].

Fig. 3. Stress-strain prediction of the plasticity model versus 30° off-axis compression test result [2].

Fig. 6. Stress-strain prediction of the plasticity model versus 75° off-axis compression test result [2].

Fig. 4. Stress-strain prediction of the plasticity model versus 45° off-axis compression test result [2].

Fig. 7. Stress-strain prediction of the plasticity model versus 90° off-axis compression test result [2].

Fig. 5. Stress-strain prediction of the plasticity model versus 60° off-axis compression test result [2].

Fig. 8. A symmetric double-notch shear (SDNS) specimen with dimensions (side and top views) [3].

Fig. 9. Illustration of limiting microscopic tensile strain in the interlaminar region for shear dominated failure on the 1-3 plane [4].

Fig. 11. The interlaminar shear failure envelope predicted by a 2D linear elastic model (single element in MATLAB), a 2D plastic model (single element in MATLAB) and a 3D plastic model (a quarter model of the actual test specimen in LS-DYNA), compared against experimental observations.

Fig. 10. (Top) A quarter FE model of the actual test specimen. (Bottom) A top view of the gauge area showing more than 50% of the area (elements in red) reaching 1.8% critical principal tensile strain as the prescribed definition of failure.